

Verification of Bhattacharya's Equation for Slow Coagulation by Turbidimetric Measurements in Ferric Oxide Sol

Iqbal A. Khan and Wahid U. Malik

Bhattacharya and Kumar¹ established the relation between the electrolyte concentration 'c' and the inverse of the corresponding time of coagulation '1/t' in the zone of slow coagulation and obtained hyperbolic curves in the majority of cases, although straight lines were obtained in some cases. The relation established by them is

$$c = a + \frac{m \times 1/t}{n + 1/t} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where *a*, *m*, and *n* are constants.

The equation on simplification assumes the following form :

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and would provide a straight line. Accordingly, a verification of the equation can be made from the coagulation data if the plots between '1/(c-a)' and 't' provide a straight line; 'a' in equation (2) is obtained from the intercepts on the c-axis from the plots of 'c' and '1/t'.

Bhattacharya and Bhattacharya² on the basis of viscometric studies assumed that the inflection points denoted the same state of aggregation of the particles in the sol. In other words, the times corresponding to the inflection point may be reasonably assumed to be such as to produce the same state of coagulation attained by adding different concentrations of the electrolyte. More or less, the same view was expressed by Troelstra and Krut³ on the basis of transmission curves. From the plots of 't' and 'galvanometer reading', sharp inflection points were realised. These points may be taken as the representative coagulation values for the different concentrations of the electrolyte added for coagulating the sol just the same way as in the viscosity experiments.

The propriety of the turbidimetric method, as employed in the present communication, in studying slow coagulation may be adjudged by applying these data to Bhattacharya's equation.

1. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 179, 638; 1952, 29, 687, 759.
2. *Kolloid Z.*, 1955, 141, 95.
3. *Kolloid Beih.*, 1943, 54, 255.

TABLE I

Ferric hydroxide and tartaric acid.

Mixtures. (b)	Conc. (c). (mM/litre)	Time (t).	1/t.	a. (mM/litre).	1/(c-a).
1	0.005	6.0 min.	0.166		1000.0
2	0.010	2.0	0.500	0.004	166.6
3	0.020	0.2	5.00		62.5
4	0.025	0.1	10.00		47.6

TABLE II

Ferric hydroxide and potassium sulphate.

Mixtures. (a)	Conc. (c). (mM/litre)	Time (t).	1/t.	a. (mM/litre)	1/(c-a).
1	0.14	5.0 min	0.2		25.0
2	0.21	2.0	0.5	0.10	9.9
3	0.28	1.0	1.0		5.9
4	0.42	0.6	1.6		3.1

The curves drawn between 'c' and '1/t' provide a hyperbola (Fig. 1, curve 1) in the case of tartaric acid and a straight line (Fig. 1, curve 2) is obtained with potassium sulphate as the coagulating electrolytes. This difference may be due to the different hydration capacity of the two ions and although the value of 'a' from the intercept on a hyperbola is likely to afford a less accurate value, the important thing is that the values of 'a', obtained in the two cases, provide straight lines for plots between '1/(c-a)' and 't' (Fig. 2, curves 3 & 4). The constants so calculated are recorded in Table III.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

Electrolytes used.	α . (mM/litre).	η . (mM/litre).	τ . (min. ⁻¹).
Tartaric acid	0.004	0.022	0.066
K ₂ SO ₄	0.100	1.000	0.900

Ferric oxide sol was prepared by the method recommended by Krecke⁴. The strength of the sol was found to be 1.75 *M* Fe₂O₃/litre. 0.1 *M*-K₂SO₄ and 0.01 *M* tartaric acid solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Mixtures prepared were: (a) 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.3 ml of 0.1 *M*-K₂SO₄ and 50 ml of sol; mixtures were made to 70 ml with requisite amounts of double distilled water; (b) 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5 ml of 0.005 *M* tartaric acid and 50 ml of the sol and mixtures were made to 100 ml with double distilled water. Turbidity measurements were carried out with Dr. Lange's turbidimeter. Curves were drawn between time 't' and the galvanometer reading.

Further light on the physical significance of these constants may be thrown when comprehensive studies with anions, especially those of the Hofmeister series, are carried out.

Thanks are due to Prof. A. R. Kidwai, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Aligarh University, Aligarh, for allowing the use of turbidimeter to carry out these studies.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ROORKEE,
ROORKEE.

Received May 25, 1964.

4. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1871, ii, 3, 286.